

Some Reactions of Nickel Chloride in N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF)

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Nickel chloride forms a 1 : 3 adduct with DMF (N,N-Dimethylformamide). Some of its reactions in DMF medium have been studied with silver nitrate, potassium thiocyanate and iodide, tri- and diethyl ammonium chloride and dimethylglyoxime. Instead of a metathetical reaction a complex formation reaction occurs with silver nitrate. Complex formation and metathetical reactions also occur with the others. With bases like tri- and diethylamine, α -picoline and pyridine base displacement reactions have been found to take place. These reactions have been found to throw light on the mode of ionisation of nickel chloride in DMF. Mostly, the results have been deduced by conductometric methods.

N,N-DIMETHYLFORMAMIDE (DMF) as a polar solvent and as a medium of reactions has been studied in recent years¹⁻²¹ and has evoked considerable interest. The present investigation deals with some reactions of nickel chloride using DMF as a reaction medium. Nickel chloride is soluble in DMF and forms a solvate having the composition $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{HCON}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ which has been isolated. Its reactions with other soluble compounds in DMF, such as silver nitrate, potassium thiocyanate and iodide, and dimethylglyoxime have been studied. It was expected that metathetical reactions resulting in the precipitation of sparingly soluble compounds in DMF viz., silver chloride and potassium chloride might result but actually the complex formation reactions also accompany them. It was also worth interesting to investigate the reactions of bases like tri- and diethylamine, α -picoline and pyridine on nickel chloride in DMF in view of an interesting solvolytic reaction with bismuth trichloride²² in an earlier studies. However, such solvolytic reaction has not been found to occur with nickel chloride. On the other hand, only a base displacement reaction takes place.

The behaviour of these reactions has evoked interest in the mode of ionisation of nickel chloride in DMF. Among the various possibilities, the most probable mechanism is the ionisation of dimeric nickel chloride in DMF as shown below :

Experimental

Purification of solvent and bases : Dimethyl formamide and bases such as triethylamine, diethylamine, α -picoline and pyridine (all B.D.H.) were purified as described in earlier studies²²⁻²⁵.

Nickel chloride adduct with dimethylformamide : 35 g of anhydrous nickel chloride was dissolved in excess of DMF (150 ml). The excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. Yellow solid of the adduct was obtained. The crystals were washed with dry carbon tetrachloride and then with dry ether. The ether was finally removed under reduced pressure. The adduct was quite stable at ordinary temperature. The solid decomposed (turns black) at 68°. The composition of the adduct was found to correspond to $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{HCON}(\text{CH}_3)_2$. Anal. Calcd. ; Ni, 16.83 ; Cl, 20.34 ; N, 12.04. Found : Ni, 16.78 ; Cl, 20.12 ; N, 11.85%.

Conductivity bridge and cell : The conductivity bridge and cell were the same as used in earlier studies^{22,23}.

Conductivity titrations : Conductometric titrations were performed in the usual manner and the conductance after applying volume corrections was plotted against the molar ratio (titrant/titrated substance).

Isolation of the nickel chloride adducts with bases : Anhydrous nickel chloride (5 g) was dissolved in 20 ml of purified base such as triethylamine, diethylamine, α -picoline or pyridine and the excess of the base removed under reduced pressure. Pale yellow coloured solids were obtained in all four cases. These were washed with dry carbon tetrachloride and then with dry ether. The ether was finally removed under reduced pressure. The samples were analysed and found to correspond to $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{B}$. The analysis is given in Table 1.

Methods of analysis : In the above compounds nickel and chlorine were determined gravimetrically as nickel dimethylglyoximate and silver chloride respectively and nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl's method.

Compound	TABLE 1					
	Theoretical(%)			Found(%)		
	Ni	Cl	N	Ni	Cl	N
NiCl ₂ ·3(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N	18.56	16.41	9.70	18.48	16.10	9.61
NiCl ₂ ·3(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ NH	16.88	20.34	12.40	16.75	20.01	12.03
NiCl ₂ ·3C ₂ H ₅ N	14.86	17.37	10.25	14.26	17.12	9.95
NiCl ₂ ·8C ₂ H ₅ N	16.01	19.36	11.45	15.90	19.30	11.12

Results and Discussion

Nickel chloride is exceedingly soluble in DMF and forms 1 : 3 adduct with DMF corresponding to NiCl₂·3HCON(CH₃)₂. Its reactions with silver nitrate, potassium thiocyanate, potassium iodide, triethyl ammonium chloride, diethyl ammonium chloride, dimethylglyoxime and some bases using DMF as a solvent medium are described below. The discussion is based mainly on the evidence derived from conductance measurements.

Reaction with silver nitrate : Silver nitrate dissolves readily in DMF and gives a white precipitate of silver chloride with a solution of nickel chloride in DMF. However, in presence of excess of nickel chloride the precipitate of silver chloride does not appear until one mole of silver nitrate per mole of nickel chloride has been added, probably due to the formation of a soluble complex Ag⁺[NiCl₂NO₃]⁻. The actually isolated compound was found to be Ag[NiCl₂·NO₃].3DMF. [Nickel chloride solution dissolves solid potassium chloride quantitatively in 1 : 1 molar ratio whereas potassium chloride is sparingly soluble in DMF. This indicates the formation of KNiCl₂, which is further supported by the conductometric titration curve (Fig. 1). The compound actually isolated corresponds to KNiCl₂·3DMF]. The conductometric titration curve (Fig. 2) of the reaction of nickel chloride with silver nitrate in DMF indicates two breaks,

Fig. 1. Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.05M NiCl₂ with solid KCl in DMF.

one at 1 : 1 molar ratio and the other at 1 : 2 molar ratio. The latter break indicates that all the two chloride ions present in the nickel chloride molecule are precipitated as silver chloride. This is also confirmed by weighing of silver chloride obtained with excess of silver nitrate. The former

Fig. 2. Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.05M NiCl₂ with 1.0M AgNO₃ in DMF.

break at 1 : 1 molar ratio can be explained by the following reaction :

Reactions with tri- and diethyl ammonium chloride : Conductometric titration of nickel chloride with tri- and diethyl ammonium chloride shows a break at 1 : 1 molar ratio indicating the formation of NiCl₂⁻ ion (Fig. 3). The solution remains clear. Further the compounds (C₂H₅)₃NH⁺[NiCl₂·3DMF]⁻ and (C₂H₅)₂NH₂⁺[NiCl₂·3DMF]⁻ were actually isolated by mixing equal volumes of equimolar solutions of tri- and diethyl ammonium chloride and nickel chloride in DMF, and then

Fig. 3. Curve 1 : Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.006M NiCl₂ with 0.1M (C₂H₅)₃NHCl in DMF. Curve 2 : Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.006M NiCl₂ with 0.1M (C₂H₅)₂NH₂Cl in DMF.

isolating the solids after removing the solvent under reduced pressure.

Reactions with potassium thiocyanate and potassium iodide : Potassium thiocyanate and potassium

iodide are soluble in DMF to the extent of about one mole per litre. Therefore, the study of the reaction between nickel chloride and potassium thiocyanate or potassium iodide is possible in DMF. The following two possibilities were expected to occur :

- (a) a metathetical reaction resulting in the precipitation of KCl as it is sparingly soluble in DMF, and
- (b) a complex formation reaction.

It has been observed that actually both categories of reactions viz., metathetical and complex formation reactions, take place when potassium thiocyanate or potassium iodide is mixed with nickel chloride in DMF. Initially no precipitate of KCl appears but it is visible after two moles of KSCN or KI for one mole of nickel chloride have been added. The reactions have been followed conductometrically and two breaks occur (Fig 4)

Fig. 4. Curve 1 : Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.05M NiCl₂ with 1.0M KSCN in DMF.
Curve 2 : Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.05M NiCl₂ with 1.0M KI in DMF.

viz., (i) at two moles which can be explained by the following equations :

and (ii) at four moles. The latter break can be explained with the help of the following equations :

Reactions with dimethylglyoxime : Dimethylglyoxime is insoluble in water. Its alcoholic solution is therefore used for the very well known reaction of nickel chloride and dimethylglyoxime in aqueous medium. When alcoholic dimethylglyoxime solution is mixed with an aqueous solution of nickel chloride, red precipitate of nickel dimethylglyoximate is formed. The reaction has

Fig. 5. Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.005M NiCl₂ with 0.1M dimethylglyoxime(alcoholic) in aqueous medium.

been followed conductometrically and a break at 1 : 2 molar ratio of nickel chloride and dimethylglyoxime has been observed (Fig. 5). The reaction can be explained with the following reaction :

Dimethylglyoxime is soluble in DMF to the extent of about 0.1 mole/litre. Therefore, the study of the reaction between nickel chloride and dimethylglyoxime is possible in a single pure solvent. It was expected that a chelate formation reaction analogous to that observed in aqueous medium may take place. However, it has been observed experimentally that a precipitate of nickel dimethylglyoximate does not appear in DMF medium and the solution remains clear even with excess of dimethylglyoxime solution. The conductometric titration curve (Fig. 6) of the reaction

Fig. 6. Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.005M NiCl₂ with 0.1M dimethylglyoxime in DMF.

of nickel chloride and dimethylglyoxime in DMF shows a break at 1 : 2 molar ratio and the break

can be explained with the help of the following reaction :

When the mixture of nickel chloride and dimethylglyoxime in DMF is treated with bases such as triethyl amine or diethyl amine, a red precipitate is obtained and this precipitate is insoluble in DMF indicating the formation of the following complex :

This type of reaction has also been studied conductometrically after preparing

by mixing nickel chloride and dimethylglyoxime in 1 : 2 molar ratio in DMF and then titrating the mixture with triethylamine (Fig. 7). The conductance increases and a break is observed at 1 : 2 molar

Fig. 7. Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.005M NiCl_2 + 2.0 ml of 0.1M dimethylglyoxime with 0.1M triethylamine in DMF.

ratio. A red precipitate of nickel dimethylglyoximate is formed during the reaction. The break can

be explained by the following equation :

The reagent dimethylglyoxime cannot be titrated with the base in DMF.

Reactions with bases : When the solution of nickel chloride in DMF is treated with bases such as triethylamine, diethylamine, α -picoline and pyridine, the solution remains clear even with excess of base. Conductometric titration curves give a sharp break at 1 : 3 molar ratio (Fig. 8). The

Fig. 8. Curve 1: Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.05M NiCl_2 with 1.0M $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}$ in DMF.
Curve 2: Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.05M NiCl_2 with 1.0M $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH}$ in DMF.
Curve 3: Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.05M NiCl_2 with 1.0M $\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N}$ (α -picoline) in DMF.
Curve 4: Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.05M NiCl_2 with 1.0M $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ in DMF.

reaction is a base displacement and may be explained by the following equation :

Nickel chloride has also been reacted with the bases such as triethylamine, diethylamine, α -picoline and pyridine separately and directly without the presence of DMF. The isolated compounds have been found to correspond to $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{B}$.

Mode of ionization of nickel chloride in DMF medium : The conductance of nickel chloride in DMF is (0.05M solution has sp. conductance 0.48×10^{-8}) much larger in comparison to that of the solvent and hence it is deduced that nickel chloride should ionize in some manner in DMF.

There are following possibilities viz., (i) $\text{NiCl}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{Ni}^{2+} + 2\text{Cl}^-$, (ii) $\text{NiCl}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NiCl}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$, (iii) $2\text{NiCl}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NiCl}^+ + \text{NiCl}_2^-$ (solvated) (solvated) (solvated) and (iv) $2\text{NiCl}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{NiCl}_2^-$ (solvated) (solvated)

The formation of highly charged ions in a solvent of relatively low dielectric constant would not seem probable as they would tend to form ion pairs and so the possibility of nickel chloride in DMF to ionise as suggested by (i) and (iv) are considered improbable. The molar conductance of nickel chloride in DMF is $62.7 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 25° . It is even less than the order of the other 1 : 1 electrolytes whose conductance has been determined in DMF. This is further supported by the fact that Shedlovsky's equation²⁴, when applied to the above system according to equation (iii) and considering nickel chloride as a dimer gives a straight line (Fig. 9) when $\frac{1}{\Delta s}$ is plotted against $c \Delta s f_{\pm}^2$. Shedlovsky's equation holds good for 1 : 1 electrolytes and since it is applicable to the above system, it may be deduced that during ionization two ions should be produced from one molecule. The mode of ionization mentioned under (iii) may fulfil the condition of Shedlovsky's plot when nickel chloride behaves as a dimer.

Fig. 9. NiCl_2

The composition of adduct of nickel chloride with DMF viz., $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{DMF}$ clearly indicates that it is not a monomer, because the usually accepted coordination number of nickel is either four or six. If nickel chloride was to be a monomer, it should have two or four moles of DMF attached to it. If dimer or trimer formulae of nickel chloride are written and the six coordination number of nickel is satisfied by attaching DMF molecules to the nickel atoms, then as shown in Fig. 10 the dimer will have the composition $[\text{NiCl}_2]_2 \cdot 6\text{DMF}$ and the trimer will have the composition $[\text{NiCl}_2]_3 \cdot 10\text{DMF}$ or $[\text{NiCl}_2]_3 \cdot 8\text{DMF}$.

The actual composition corresponds to the dimer and hence the dimeric nature of nickel chloride DMF adduct in the solid state may be reasonably assumed.

In view of the above consideration the most probable mode of ionization is as suggested under

(iii) viz.,

The mode of ionization under (ii) is not likely in view of the fact that it would require nickel chloride DMF adduct to be a monomer. Further, the formation of $[\text{NiCl}_2]^-$ ion (*loc. cit.*) support the above suggested mode of ionization for the nickel chloride in DMF.

Fig. 10 (c) Trimer $[\text{NiCl}_2]_3 \cdot 8\text{DMF}$

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